

Synthesis of Some 2-(Thiazol-2-yl-aminomethyl-) Benzimidazoles

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In extension of our earlier work¹, the synthesis of benzimidazoles, substituted in position 2 with thiazole ring, has been undertaken. Bloom and Day² prepared 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole and replaced the highly active chlorine by methylamino, diethylamino, pyrrolidino, piperidino, morpholino, and other groups by condensing with the corresponding primary and secondary amines. Some of these compounds were reported as local anaesthetics. Turk and Ueckert³ prepared 2-(4-thiazolyl)benzimidazole and reported its use as anthelmintic for horses. Cairns⁴ has described the compound as a powerful anthelmintic for sheep. In view of the above observations and well-known therapeutic properties of thiazole ring, it was considered worthwhile to undertake synthesis of 2-(thiazol-2-yl-aminomethyl-)benzimidazoles for testing purposes.

The condensation of 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole and 2-aminothiazole can take the course (I) or (II). It is well established that in presence of sodamide, the condensation of such nuclei is prevented *via* the imino form⁵ and thus the possibility of the formation of product (II) is excluded.

2-(Thiazol-2-yl-aminomethyl-)benzimidazoles (Table I) have been obtained by the condensation of 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole with 2-amino-4-methyl-(I), 2-amino-

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1. Gupta and Singh, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 667.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, 4, 14.

3. *J. Amer. Vet. Med. Assoc.*, 1933., 141, 240.

4. *New Zealand Vet. J.*, 1961, 8, 147.

5. Chhabra *et al.*, *Rev.*, 1921, 54B, 814.

4,5-dimethyl-(II), 2-amino-5-ethyl-4-methyl-(III), 2-amino-4-phenyl-(IV), 2-amino-4-(*p*-tolyl)-(V), 2-amino-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-(VI), 2-amino-5-methyl-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-(VII), 2-amino-4-(2-nitro-*p*-tolyl)-(VIII), 2-anilino-4-methyl-(IX), 2-anilino-4,5-dimethyl-(X), 2-anilino-4-phenyl-(XI), 2-anilino-4-(*p*-tolyl)-(XII), 2-anilino-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-(XIII), 2-anilino-5-methyl-4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-(XIV), and 2-anilino-4-(2-nitro-*p*-tolyl)-(XV) thiazoles in presence of sodamide, using dioxane as the solvent.

2-Aminothiazoles have been prepared by the method of Dodson and King⁶. 2-Chloromethylbenzimidazole has been obtained by refluxing *o*-phenylenediamine with chloroacetic acid in presence of 4*N*-HCl⁷.

2-Aminothiazoles.—A mixture of appropriate ketone (0.2*M*), thiourea (0.4*M*), and iodine (0.2 *M*) was refluxed on a water bath for about 8 hr. Heating was continued for another 18 to 24 hr. without condenser. The reaction product was then allowed to remain with ether for 48 hr. to remove the unchanged ketone. The excess of iodine was removed with a sodium thiosulphate solution. The hydroiodide was dissolved in water, filtered, and the clear filtrate was neutralised with concentrated ammonium hydroxide. The precipitated free base, 2-aminothiazole, was crystallised from ethanol.

2-(Thiazol-2-yl-aminomethyl)-benzimidazoles.—A mixture of the appropriate 2-aminothiazole (0.1*M*) and sodamide (0.1*M*) in dioxane (30 ml) was heated for 2 hr. and 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole (0.1*M*) added in small quantities. Heating was continued for 3 to 4 hr. and the product was treated with HCl (conc.). The precipitated hydrochloride was

TABLE I

2-(Thiazol-2-yl-aminomethyl)-benzimidazoles.

R ₁ .	R ₂ .	R ₃ .	% Yield.	*M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Me	H	H	65	211°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	22.52	22.05	12.04	12.11
Me	Me	H	70	172°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	21.20	21.70	12.22	12.40
Me	Et	H	70	104°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	20.25	20.59	11.54	11.76
Ph	H	H	55	121°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	18.01	18.20	10.42	10.45
<i>p</i> -Tol	H	H	50	221°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	17.32	17.50	9.58	10.00
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	H	H	65	162°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ BrS	14.46	14.54	8.06	8.21
"	Me	H	55	241°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ BrS	12.71	14.03	7.94	8.02
2-Nitro- <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	H	60	175°	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₅ S	18.87	19.17	8.43	8.76
Me	H	Ph	60	191°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	17.34	17.50	9.64	10.00
Me	Me	Ph	65	173°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	16.32	16.71	9.16	9.53
Ph	H	Ph	60	224°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	14.20	14.65	8.09	8.37
<i>p</i> -Tol	H	Ph	60	> 300°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	13.78	14.16	8.00	8.08
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	H	Ph	60	184°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₄ BrS	11.84	12.14	6.82	6.94
"	Me	Ph	70	151°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ BrS	11.43	11.79	6.20	6.72
2-Nitro- <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	Ph	75	121°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ S	15.59	15.87	7.04	7.25

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242.

7. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2283.

removed, dissolved in water, and neutralised with ammonium hydroxide to liberate the free base. It was then crystallised from dilute ethanol or a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate.

The authors are thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the financial assistance and for the award of a fellowship to one of them (J. S.). The authors are also grateful to the Head of the Chemistry Department and authorities of Meerut College for the facilities provided during the investigation.

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Received November 28, 1964.